

(Re)Building Trust. Will visible Open Science Practices foster perceived integrity of journal articles?

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ABSTRACT

Keywords

Open Science Practices; Badges; Trustworthiness; Epistemic Beliefs

Purpose of this paper

The Replication Crisis diminishes trust in empirical sciences and with it the perceived value of science (Lupia, 2018). Open Science Practices (i.e. open data, open analysis script, open materials) are an increasingly popular approach to deal with challenges in replication and to rebuilt trust (Geukes, Schönbrodt, Utesch, Geukes, & Back, 2016). Trusting the integrity of researchers is particularly significant within professions that include reflections on evidence-based actions, like in teaching (Cochran-Smith, 2009). First investigations could, however, deliver no evidence toward the effects of Open Science Practices (OSP) on trustworthiness (Wingen, Berkessel, & English, 2019). The study investigated the effect on a discipline level (psychology) with an abstract description of OSP. Within the ongoing discussion about incentives for OSP (e.g. badges), we want to shift the focus from discipline level to concrete individual journal articles and consider epistemic beliefs of readers to play a moderating role (Merk & Rosman, 2018): Will visible OSP (vs. not visible vs. visibly non-OSP) foster perceived

trustworthiness when reading journal articles of empirical studies? Will multiplistic epistemic beliefs moderate the relationship between OSP and trustworthiness?

Confirmatory, H1: Visible OSP (vs. not visible vs. visibly non-OSP) influence the perceived trustworthiness (subscale integrity) in the empirical study. Our assumption: The more openness, the more trustworthy with small to moderate effects: $\mu_1 < \mu_2 < \mu_3$

Confirmatory, H2: The higher the (topic specific) multiplistic epistemic beliefs, the lower the perceived trustworthiness (subscale integrity). Negative correlation.

Exploratory, H3: (Topic specific) multiplistic epistemic beliefs moderate the effect of OSP on perceived trustworthiness (subscale integrity).

Exploratory, H4: Visible OSP (vs. not visible vs. visibly non-OSP) have a negative effect on topic specific multiplism.

Design/methodology/approach

The design will include three conditions: visible Open Science Practices (visOSP), Practices not visible (nonvis) and visible non-Open Science Practices (nonOSP). Two of the three conditions are randomized within person. Realizing all three conditions within person would highlight the variation between conditions as too obvious and thus undermine blinding of subjects.

visOSP condition: Subjects receive a title page of an empirical study (Title, Abstract, Keywords, Introduction, ...) together with three Open Science badges. The badges are explained using hints in style of speech bubbles and indicate that the authors engaged in the OSP open data, open analysis script and open materials.

nonvis condition: Subjects receive a title page of an empirical study (Title, Abstract, Keywords, Introduction, ...) with no further information on Open Science, reflecting a "standard" journal article. For comparability purposes speech bubbles are used as well, giving information on keywords, volume/ issue and abstract.

nonOSP condition: Subjects receive a title page of an empirical study (Title, Abstract, Keywords, Introduction, ...) together with three Open Science badges. The badges are explained using hints in style of speech bubbles and indicate that the authors did not engage in the OSP open data, open analysis script and open materials.

As participants are exposed to more than one condition, we create all three conditions for two different empirical studies (topics). This way we avoid participants to see one study topic twice under different treatment conditions, which would undermine the blinding (see title pages here: gitlab.com/j_Schneider/re-building-trust/tree/master/3_design).

Measured variables are *perceived trustworthiness*: We apply the Muenster Epistemic Trustworthiness Inventory (Hendriks, Kienhues, & Bromme, 2015) with all three subscales. However, as dependent variable we will only employ the subscale integrity. The other two subscales are used for further exploratory analyses. *Topic specific multiplistic epistemic beliefs*: We apply the subscale of topic specific multiplism from Merk et al. (2017). *Topic-specific consistency*: We apply the three item-measure from Merk et al. (2017). *Treatment check*: We created five items to test the perceived openness/ transparency of the empirical study. A sample Likert item (four-point scale “disagree” to “agree”) is “It is transparent which performance tests and data underlie the study.” A second treatment check with three Likert items (four-point scale “disagree” to “agree”) investigates the perception of the speech bubbles explaining the badges. Sample item: “On the title pages I read all the additional annotations (grey boxes).” Additional small set of *demographic variables* (age, sex, location of teacher education program) will be assessed.

We conducted Bayes Factor Design Analyses: osf.io/gu58n/. As conditions are rotated (participants receive 2 out of 3 conditions), we conducted BFDA for two t-tests. Required sample size for small to medium effect, stopping rule of Bayes Factor of 10 (1/10 respectively) and 80% Power are $N = 220$. We thus aim for a $N_{\max} = 250$ with optional stopping at BF 10 or 1/10 respectively. Due to expected variations in the BF with low n , we begin observing the data at $n = 150$. As argued above, perceived trustworthiness of empirical evidence appears particularly significant within the teacher profession and teacher preparation programs. Data will thus be collected from the population of pre-service teachers using monetary incentives for participation.

Findings/expected Findings

For the data analyses, we plan to use an Informative Hypotheses Approach based on our abovementioned assumptions. Data analysis scripts including the `bain` package (Gu, Hoijtink, Mulder, & Lissa, 2019) are available on <https://osf.io/32duk>.

OSF-Project: osf.io/vgbrs/

GitLab: gitlab.com/j_schneider/re-building-trust.git

Preregistration (14.06.): osf.io/2zypf

Research limitations/implications

Our sample will be gathered from the population of pre-service teachers. Further research would thus need to include other populations (e.g. in-service teachers, medicine students) to ensure external validity. Moreover, the title pages with the badges are tested for two specific topics within teacher education. More data on a broader range of topics would be desirable. We also didn't plan to inform our subjects on the Replication Crisis. Future research could investigate effects of diminished trust through the crisis with subsequent effects of visible OSP in journal articles.

Practical implications

The study investigates the effects of badges (visible OPS) in journal articles.

Social implications

The study investigates lay peoples trust and thus value of scientific research.

What is original/value of paper

The paper allows insights into the effectiveness of the visibility of OSP through a robust research design.

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References

- Cochran-Smith, M. & Boston College Evidence Team. (2009). "Re-Culturing" Teacher Education: Inquiry, Evidence, and Action. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 60(5), 458–468. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022487109347206>
- Geukes, K., Schönbrodt, F. D., Utesch, T., Geukes, S., & Back, M. D. (2016). Wege aus der Vertrauenskrise: Individuelle Schritte hin zu verlässlicher und offener Forschung. *Zeitschrift für Sportpsychologie*, 23(3), 99–109. <https://doi.org/10.1026/1612-5010/a000167>
- Gu, X., Hoijtink, H., Mulder, J., & Lissa, C. J. van. (2019). *bain: Bayes Factors for Informative Hypotheses*. Abgerufen von <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=bain>

- Hendriks, F., Kienhues, D., & Bromme, R. (2015). Measuring Laypeople's Trust in Experts in a Digital Age: The Muenster Epistemic Trustworthiness Inventory (METI). *PLOS ONE*, *10*(10), e0139309. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0139309>
- Lupia, A. (2018). The Role of Transparency in Maintaining the Legitimacy and Credibility of Survey Research. In D. L. Vannette & J. A. Krosnick (Hrsg.), *The Palgrave Handbook of Survey Research* (S. 315–318). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-54395-6_41
- Merk, S., & Rosman, T. (2018). *Smart but evil? Student-teachers perception of educational researchers' epistemic trustworthiness*. [Preprint]. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/cduqe>
- Merk, S., Rosman, T., Rueß, J., Syring, M., & Schneider, J. (2017). Pre-service teachers' perceived value of general pedagogical knowledge for practice: Relations with epistemic beliefs and source beliefs. *PloS one*, *12*(9), 0184971. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0184971>
- Wingen, T., Berkessel, J., & Englich, B. (2019). *No Replication, no Trust? How Low Replicability Influences Trust in Psychology* [Preprint]. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/4ukq5>

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